

IMPACT OF BURNOUT ON THE ADVERSITY RESPONSE LEVEL OF POLICE OFFICERS: A PROPOSED INTERVENTION MEASURE

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to explore the impact of burnout levels on the Adversity Response Quotient (ARQ) of police officers in Bohol, with the objective of developing an effective intervention measure. The research examined the demographic profile of police officers, including factors such as age, gender, marital status, length of service, educational attainment, number of children, and dependents. Additionally, the study assessed the ARQ of the officers and analyzed their levels of burnout across three subscales: emotional exhaustion, personal accomplishment, and depersonalization. The findings revealed that the majority of respondents were male, aged 30 to 40, and married, with a service length of 6 to 15 years. Most officers were college graduates and had 1 to 3 children or dependents. The ARQ of police officers was found to be at an average level, indicating that they often felt in control and responsible for adverse situations, although these situations sometimes affected their lives. In terms of burnout, police officers experienced emotional exhaustion and depersonalization once a month or less, while feelings of personal accomplishment occurred once a week. The study found no significant relationship between the demographic profile and ARQ. However, the number of children was significantly correlated with burnout levels. Importantly, no significant correlation was found between the ARQ and burnout levels. Based on these conclusions, the study recommends that the Philippine National Police establish a platform for officers to report emotional or mental stress, along with organizing mental health seminars. It also suggests that police stations collaborate with mental health institutions to promote effective coping strategies and foster a supportive culture that addresses officers' mental

well-being. Future research could further explore the role of social support in mitigating burnout and enhancing ARQ among police officers.

Keywords: *Adversity Response Quotient (ARQ), Burnout, Coping Strategies, Mental Health, and Police Officers*

INTRODUCTION

The law enforcement profession is widely recognized for its demanding and stressful nature, characterized by unique responsibilities and inherent risks. Police officers are tasked with maintaining public safety, protecting property, and safeguarding lives. However, their roles extend far beyond these fundamental duties, often involving unpredictable and high-stress situations such as routine traffic stops and complex emergency responses, which significantly contribute to stress levels (Violanti et al., 2017; McCarty & Skogan, 2013; Papazoglou & Tuttle, 2018; Nwaonumah, 2018). This constant exposure to potentially traumatic events, combined with the authority to use force—including deadly force—often leads to burnout. Burnout is characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment, which adversely affects both officers' mental health and the quality of their service (Maslach & Leiter, 2016; Carleton et al., 2018; Engelken, 2019). Addressing burnout is crucial for ensuring effective policing and supporting officers' well-being.

In today's multifaceted law enforcement environment, officers navigate multiple roles, including those of first responders and social workers, adding layers of complexity to their stress management (Mayfield, 2019; Papazoglou & Tuttle, 2018). The concept of adversity, as defined by Venkatesh & Shivaranjani (2016), encompasses societal, workplace, and individual challenges that contribute to the stress experienced by law enforcement personnel. Understanding how resilience—a critical factor in coping with adversity—affects officers' ability to manage stress is crucial (Bullock & Garland, 2018). Resilience allows individuals to adapt to challenging circumstances and recover from setbacks, which is vital in high-stress professions (Smith & Lazarus, 1993). The Adversity Quotient (AQ), developed by Stoltz (2018), measures an individual's capacity to handle and overcome adversity. Higher AQ scores are associated with better resilience and stress management (Venkatesh & Shivaranjani (2016).

Additionally, research by Anshel et al. (2019) on occupational stress highlights how prolonged exposure to uncontrollable stressors can lead to feelings of helplessness and reduced motivation. This concept is particularly relevant to law enforcement, where officers may experience a loss of control over their work environment, contributing to burnout and decreased job satisfaction. Furthermore, Maslach and Leiter (2016) emphasize the importance of organizational interventions to address burnout, including support systems and workload management, to enhance officers' well-being and effectiveness.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of burnout on the adversity quotient of police officers and to understand how these factors influence their stress response and overall well-being. By examining the relationship between burnout and AQ, this research aims to provide insights into how law enforcement personnel cope with the challenges of their profession. Additionally, this study seeks to contribute to the development of strategies that can improve working conditions, enhance job satisfaction, and ultimately support the well-being of officers. Through a comprehensive analysis of these dynamics, the study aims to offer recommendations for improving stress management and resilience among law enforcement professionals, thereby enhancing their ability to serve and protect the community effectively.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the impact of burnout levels on the Adversity Response Quotient of police officers, with the goal of proposing an intervention measure. Specifically, it sought to answer the following subproblems:

1. What is the demographic profile of police officers along?
 - a. Age;
 - b. Gender;
 - c. Marital Status;
 - d. Length of Service;
 - e. Highest educational level;
 - f. Number of children; and
 - g. Number of people dependent on financial support?
2. What is the Adversity Response Profile of police officers?
3. What is the level of Burnout experienced by police officers?
4. Is there a significant degree of correlation between Adversity Quotient and Burnout?
5. What intervention measure can be developed for police officers?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher employed a descriptive-correlational design using quantitative methods. The descriptive approach was utilized to assess the burnout levels of police officers across three areas: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal accomplishment. Additionally, the Adversity Quotient was evaluated along four dimensions: control, ownership, reach, and endurance. The correlational method was used to examine the relationship between burnout levels and the adversity quotient profile of police officers.

Research Environment and Participants

This study was conducted in 2019 and involved both commissioned and non-commissioned police officers from the Bohol Provincial Police Office. The research covered the entire Bohol Provincial Police Office organization.

Research Instrument

Two major instruments were used to obtain the answer of the presented problem: the online Adversity Quotient 9:1 (AQP) and Burnout Inventory.

The first questionnaire is on the Adversity Quotient Profile or Adversity Response Profile version 9.1 developed by Dr. Paul G Stoltz of Peak Learning, Inc. California. The Stoltz' ARP version 9.1 (2009) is a self-rating questionnaire that measures the individual's adversity level in responding with different adverse situations. The questionnaire provided by the Peak Learning, Inc. is an online data input which presents 14 scenarios or events; each is followed by 4 questions with 5-point Likert Scale. The online questionnaire is accessible through the private URL designated for the researcher and created by the Peak Learning, Inc., just for the purpose of this study. After the online submission of the responses, the descriptive interpretations of AQP were sent by Stoltz with the use of the electronic spreadsheet.

Adversity Quotient

Score Range and Equivalent Score Range Equivalent

176-200	High
158-175	Above Average
136-157	Average
119-135	Below Average
40-118	Low

The explanation of the verbal interpretation is as follows:

Low- The person probably suffers unnecessarily in number of ways. The motivation, energy, vitality, health, performance, persistence, and hope can be greatly revitalized by learning and practicing the tools in raising AQ.

Below Average- The person is likely to be under-utilizing his potential. Adversity can take a significant and unnecessary toll, making it difficult to continue the ascent. The person may battle against a sense of helplessness and despair. Escape is possible by raising the AQ.

Average- The person usually does descent job of navigating life as long everything is going relatively smooth. However, the person may suffer unnecessarily from larger setbacks, or maybe disheartened by the accumulated burden of life's challenges.

Above Average- The person has probably done a fairly good job in persisting through challenges and in tapping a good portion of growing potential on a daily basis.

High- The person probably has the ability to withstand significant adversity and to continue to move forward and upward in life.

On the other hand, the MBI-GS was the instrument used to determine the level of burnout in the organization that was the subject of the study. The MBI-GS consists of 16 statements describing the feelings an individual might have as a result of being over-stressed or burned out. Respondents were asked to indicate the frequency which they experienced these feelings by selecting from a list of six response choices: 0=never; 1= few times a year or less; 2= Once a month or less; 3=A few times a month; 4= Once a week; 5= A few times a week; and 6= Everyday.

The MBI-GS measures burnout on three sub-scales: (a) Emotional Exhaustion, including references to fatigue, but with no direct references to people being the source of fatigue, (b) -15- Cynicism, an indifferent or distant attitude toward work and referring to the work itself and not to personal relationships at work, and (c) Professional Efficacy, encompassing both social and non-social aspects of organizational accomplishments and expectations of continued effectiveness at work.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher adhered to a series of procedures to gather data for this study. Initially, permission to use the Adversity Response Profile version 9.1 was obtained from Dr. Paul G. Stoltz of Peak Learning, Inc. in California via email. Following the submission and signing of the agreement contract with Peak Learning, Inc., the researcher also secured authorization to conduct the study from Superintendent Angeles Genorga, Director of the Bohol Provincial Police Office.

Subsequently, the researcher organized and conducted brief orientations for each district, instructing participants on how to complete the Adversity Quotient (AQ) Profile and Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) questionnaires online. The timing of these survey administrations was scheduled based on the researcher's availability.

Data Analysis

The researcher utilized the following statistical tools in the process of data obtained through the questionnaires:

Frequency-Percentage was used in determining the profile of the respondents in terms of demographic variables (age, gender, marital status, length of service, highest educational level, number of children, and number of people dependent on financial support), Adversity Quotient, and MBI.

The Adversity Quotient Profile of the police officers was tabulated including their four dimensions: control, ownership, reach and endurance. Similarly, the means on the MBI profile was also tabulated.

Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, means and inferential statistics like chi-square test were used to analyze the data. To determine the relationship between the responses of the respondents on the Adversity Quotient and burnout level of police officers, the chi-square test of contingency was used.

$$x^2 = \sum \frac{(f_o - f_e)^2}{f_e}$$

Where: X = Chi -square factor

f_o = observed frequency

f_e = expected or theoretical frequency

RESULTS

This chapter provides an analysis and interpretation of the data collected, focusing on various aspects of the problem. It begins with an examination of the demographic profiles of the police officers, followed by an analysis of their Adversity Response Profile and the levels of burnout they experience. Finally, the chapter explores the correlation between the Adversity Quotient and the burnout levels experienced by the police officers.

Table I. Distribution of Respondent

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Police Officer	280	100

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondent. There are 280 respondent police officers in this study which is equivalent to a 100% of the respondents.

Table II. Demographic Profile of Respondents.

Items	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
A. Age			
25 years old and below	3	1.07	5
26-30 years old	71	25.36	2
31-40 years old	131	46.78	1
41-50 years old	57	20.36	3
51 years old and above	18	6.43	4
Total	280	100	
B. Gender			
Male	175	62.50	1
Female	105	37.50	2
Total	280	100	
C. Marital Status			
Single	49	17.50	2
Married	225	80.36	1
Widow	6	2.14	3
Separated	0	0	
Total	280	100	
D. Length of Service			
Below 5 years	53	18.3	3

6-10 years	88	31.43	1
11-15 years	64	22.86	2
16-20 years	40	14.28	4
21-25 years	20	7.14	5
26-30 years	15	5.36	6
Total	280	100	
E. Educational Attainment			
College Level	4	1/43	2
College Graduate	271	96.79	1
Masters with Units	0	0	
Master Degree Holder	3	1.07	3
LLB with Units	2	0.7	4
Ph.D. with Units	0	0	
Total	280	100	
F. No. of Children			
None	54	19.29	2
1-3	286	66.43	1
4-6	51	12.85	3
7-10	8	1.43	4
Total	280	100	
G. No. of Dependents			
None	39	13.93	3
1-3	182	65.00	1
4-6	51	18.21	2
7-10	8	2.86	4
Total	280	100	

Table 2 displays the demographic profile of the respondents, including their age, gender, marital status, length of service, educational attainment, and number of children or dependents. The table presents the frequency, percentage, and rank for each demographic category.

According to Table 2, approximately 46% of the police officers are between the ages of 30 and 40, 25% are aged 26 to 30, and 20% fall within the 41 to 50 age range. The gender distribution reveals that 62.5% of the officers are male and 37.5% are female. Marital status data indicates that around 80% of the respondents are married. Regarding their length of service, the majority have served for 6 to 15 years. Educationally, about 96% of the respondents hold a college degree. Lastly, most of the respondents have between 1 and 3 children or dependents.

Table III.
Adversity Quotient Profile of Police Officers

ITEMS	5		4		3		2		1		WM	Desc	Rank
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%			
1. You suffer a financial setback.	72	25.71	53	18.93	88	31.43	65	23.21	2	0.71	3.45	QP	10
2. You are overlooked for a promotion.	140	50.00	39	13.93	66	23.57	30	10.71	5	1.78	4.00	QP	1
3. You are criticized for a big project that you just completed.	22	7.86	46	16.43	155	55.36	51	18.21	6	2.14	3.10	BLS	20
4. You accidentally delete an important email.	37	13.21	84	30.00	92	32.86	56	21.43	11	3.93	3.28	BLS	15.5
5. The high-priority project you are working on gets canceled.	32	11.43	66	23.57	136	48.57	40	14.28	6	2.14	3.28	BLS	15.5
6. Someone you respect ignores your attempt to discuss an important issue.	69	24.64	66	23.57	84	30.00	52	18.57	9	3.21	3.48	QP	7.5
7. People respond unfavorably to your latest ideas.	42	15.00	64	22.86	107	38.21	55	19.64	12	4.28	3.25	BLS	17
8. You are unable to take a much-needed vacation.	28	10.00	102	36.43	106	37.86	37	13.21	7	2.50	3.38	BLS	11.5
9. You hit every red light on your way to an important appointment.	30	10.71	34	12.14	160	57.14	50	17.86	6	2.14	3.11	BLS	19
10. After extensive searching, you cannot find an important document.	90	32.14	90	32.14	52	18.57	40	14.28	8	2.86	3.76	QP	4
11. Your workplace is understaffed.	123	43.93	43	15.36	67	23.93	33	11.78	14	5.00	3.81	QP	3
12. You miss an important appointment	41	14.64	55	19.64	123	43.93	52	18.57	9	3.21	3.24	BLS	18
13. Your personal and work obligations are out of balance.	71	25.36	67	23.93	88	31.43	46	16.43	8	2.86	3.52	QP	5.5
14. You never seem to have enough money.	42	15.00	107	38.21	82	29.28	43	15.36	6	2.14	3.48	QP	7.5
15. You are not exercising regularly though you know you should.	65	23.21	61	21.78	80	28.57	64	22.86	10	3.57	3.38	BLS	11.5
16. Your organization is not meeting its goals.	117	41.78	56	21.43	64	22.86	35	12.50	8	2.86	3.85	QP	2
17. Your computer crashed for the third time this week.	80	28.57	58	20.71	75	26.78	46	16.43	21	7.50	3.46	QP	9
18. The meeting you are in is a total waste of time.	60	21.43	61	21.78	87	31.07	47	16.78	25	8.93	3.30	BLS	14
19. You lost something that is important to you.	45	16.07	108	38.57	80	28.57	43	15.36	4	2.43	3.52	QP	5.5
20. Your boss adamantly disagrees with your decision.	32	11.43	65	23.21	146	52.14	32	11.43	5	1.78	3.31	BLS	13
Average Weighted Mean											3.44	QP	

Legend:

#	Description	Code	Range
5	Completely Responsible	CR	4.21-5.00
4	Quickly Pass	QP	3.41-4.20
3	Be Limited to this Situation	BLS	2.61-3.40
2	Responsible	R	1.81-2.60
1	Not Responsible at All	NR	1.00-1.80

Table 3 presents the Adversity Quotient Profile of Police Officers. 5 means completely responsible with a score range of 4.21 to 5.00. 4 means quickly pass with a score range of 3.41 to 4.20. Meanwhile, 3 means be limited to this situation with a score range of 2.61 to 3.40. 2 means responsible with a score range of 1.81 to 2.60 and 1 means not responsible at all with a score of 1.0 to 1.80.

The table shows that the item #2 which said ‘You are overlooked for a promotion’ got the highest weighted mean 4.00 with the corresponding description “Quickly Pass” within the range of 3.41-4.20. The frequency of item # 2 consisted of 140 which described as completely responsible within the range 4.21-5.00, 39 as quickly pass within the range 3.41-4.20, 66 be limited to this situation was within the range 2.61-3.40, 30 was described responsible within the range 1.81-2.60, and 5 was described as not responsible at all within the range 1.0-1.80. resulting an average weighted mean 3.4 which meant “Quickly Pass or (QP)”.

Table IV
Responses of Police Officers on the Specific Dimensions on this Adversity Quotient
(N=280)

A. Control

ITEMS	5 (4.21-5.00)		4 (3.41-4.20)		3 (2.61-3.40)		2 (1.81-2.60)		1 (1.0-1.80)		Weighted Mean	Description	Rank
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%			
3	22	7.86	46	16.43	155	55.36	51	18.21	6	2.14	3.10	BLS	5
6	69	24.64	66	23.57	84	30.00	52	18.57	9	3.21	3.48	QP	3
15	65	23.21	61	21.78	80	28.86	54	22.86	10	3.57	3.38	BLS	4
16	117	41.79	56	20.00	64	22.86	35	12.50	8	2.86	3.85	QP	1
19	45	16.07	108	38.57	80	28.57	43	15.36	4	1.43	3.52	QP	2
Average Weighted Mean											3.46	QP-Quickly Pass	

B. Ownership

Items	5 (4.21-5.00)		4 (3.41-4.20)		3 (2.61-3.40)		2 (1.81-2.60)		1 (1.0-1.80)		Weighted Mean	Description	Rank
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%			
2	140	50.00	39	13.93	66	23.57	30	10.71	5	1.78	4.00	QP	1
7	42	15.00	64	22.86	38.21	38.21	55	19.64	12	4.28	3.25	BLS	5
10	90	32.14	90	32.14	18.57	18.57	40	14.28	8	2.86	3.76	QP	2
14	42	15.00	107	38.21	29.28	29.28	43	15.36	6	2.14	3.48	QP	3
17	80	28.57	58	20.71	26.78	26.78	46	16.43	21	7.50	3.46	QP	4
Average Weighted Mean											3.59	QP – Quickly Pass	

C. Reach

Items	5 (4.21-5.00)		4 (3.41-4.20)		3 (2.61-3.40)		2 (1.81-2.60)		1 (1.0-1.80)		Weighted Mean	Description	Rank
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%			
4	37	13.21	84	30.00	92	32.86	56	20.00	11	3.93	3.28	BLS	3
9	30	10.71	34	12.14	160	57.14	50	17.86	6	2.14	3.11	BLS	5
11	13	43.93	43	15.36	67	23.93	33	11.78	14	5.00	3.81	QP	1
12	41	1.64	55	19.64	123	43.93	52	18.57	9	3.21	3.24	BLS	4
13	71	25.36	67	23.93	88	31.43	46	16.43	8	2.86	3.52	QP	2
Average Weighted Mean											3.392	BLS – Be Limited to this Situation	

D. Endurance

Items	5 (4.21-5.00)		4 (3.41-4.20)		3 (2.61-3.40)		2 (1.81-2.60)		1 (1.0-1.80)		Weighted Mean	Description	Rank
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%			
1	72	25.71	53	18.93	88	31.43	65	23.21	2	.71	3.45	QP	1
5	32	11.43	66	23.57	136	48.57	40	14.28	6	2.14	3.28	BLS	5
8	28	10.00	102	36.43	106	37.86	37	13.21	7	2.50	3.38	BLS	2
18	60	21.43	61	21.78	87	31.00	47	16.78	25	8.93	3.30	BLS	4
20	32	11.43	65	23.21	146	52.14	32	11.43	5	1.78	3.31	BLS	3
Average Weighted Mean											3.344	BLS–Be Limited to this Situation	

Table 4 highlights that police officers generally have a moderate sense of control over adverse situations, with an average weighted mean score of 3.46. Item 16 stands out with the highest mean score of 3.85, indicating that officers often feel they can manage adversity effectively. Other items, such as Items 6 and 19, with scores of 3.48 and 3.52 respectively, also show that while officers frequently perceive themselves as controlling situations, there is some variability in their sense of control. Overall, the data suggests that officers can handle adversity well but may encounter challenges in consistently applying control across all situations.

In terms of Ownership, it reveals that police officers exhibit a strong sense of personal responsibility, reflected in an average weighted mean score of 3.59. Item 2, with the highest mean score of 4.00, indicates that officers frequently feel accountable for the situations they face. Items 7 and 10, with scores of 3.25 and 3.76 respectively, further demonstrate that while many officers take ownership of their challenges, there are varying levels of engagement. The overall trend suggests that officers predominantly embrace responsibility for their adversities, though some differences in the extent of this ownership exist.

The Reach dimension, with an average weighted mean score of 3.39, shows that police officers generally manage to limit the impact of adverse situations on other areas of their lives. Item 11, scoring 3.81, indicates that officers often confine adversity to specific situations. However, Items 4 and 13, with scores of 3.28 and 3.52 respectively, suggest that while officers are generally effective in managing the reach of adversity, there are instances where challenges may affect broader aspects of their lives. The results reflect a balanced approach to handling adversity, with occasional lapses where issues might spread beyond the immediate context.

Regarding Endurance, it shows that police officers perceive adverse situations as having a moderate duration, with an average weighted mean score of 3.34. Item 1, with a score of 3.45, indicates that officers often view adversities as passing relatively quickly. Items 5 and 8, with scores of 3.28 and 3.38 respectively, reveal that while many officers see challenges as temporary, some perceive them as more prolonged. Overall, the data suggests that officers generally maintain hope and optimism despite encountering enduring difficulties, although there are variations in how long they perceive these adversities to last.

Table V
Correlation Between Police Officers' Adversity Quotient Response Profile and Their Corresponding Demographic Profile

A. Age

Age	Adversity Quotient Response Profile					Total
	Completely Responsible (4.21-5.0)	Quickly Pass (3.41-4.20)	Be limited to this Situation (2.61-3.40)	Responsible (1.81-2.60)	Not Responsible (1.0-1.80)	
25 years old and below	1	1	1	0	0	3
26-30 years old	2	30	33	5	1	71
31-40 years old	4	62	58	5	2	131
41-50 years old	2	22	31	2	0	57
51 years old and above	0	9	9	0	0	18
Total	9	124	132	12	3	280

The data on adversity quotient response profiles across different age groups reveals notable patterns. Individuals aged 25 years and below demonstrates a relatively balanced response profile, with equal representation in the categories of "Completely Responsible," "Quickly Pass," and "Be Limited to this Situation," totaling three responses.

In contrast, the 26-30 years age group shows a predominance of "Quickly Pass" responses, with 30 out of 71 individuals in this category, indicating a tendency to handle adversity with moderate responsibility. The 31-40 years age group exhibits the highest level of responsibility overall, with 62 individuals categorized as "Quickly Pass" and 4 as "Completely Responsible," reflecting a more mature and responsible approach to adversity. The 41-50 years age group shows a decline in the most responsible responses, with fewer individuals categorized as "Completely Responsible" and a moderate number in other categories. Finally, those aged 51 years and above have the least number of responses but display a notable presence in the "Quickly Pass" and "Be Limited to this Situation" categories, suggesting a varied but less responsible approach to adversity compared to younger age groups.

B. Gender

Gender	Adversity Quotient Response Profile					
	Completely Responsible	Quickly Pass	Be Limited to this Situation	Responsible	Not Responsible at all	Total
Male	4	81	83	6	1	175
Female	5	44	47	7	2	105
Total	9	12.5	130	13	3	280

The data on adversity quotient response profiles by gender indicates that males generally exhibit a higher level of responsibility compared to females. Males have a notable number of responses in the "Quickly Pass" and "Be Limited to this Situation" categories, with 81 and 83 individuals respectively, while females have fewer responses in these categories (44 and 47). Both genders show similar levels in the "Completely Responsible" category, with males at 4 and females at 5. However, males have slightly more individuals categorized as "Not Responsible at all" (1) compared to females (2). Overall, males show a more varied response profile with a higher total count in each category, reflecting a broader spectrum of adversity handling compared to females.

C. Marital Status

Marital Status	Adversity Quotient Response Profile					
	Completely Responsible	Quickly Pass	Be Limited to this Situation	Responsible	Not Responsible at all	Total
Single	1	20	26	1	0	48
Married	8	102	100	12	3	225
Widow	0	3	4	0	0	7
Separated	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	9	125	130	13	3	280

The data on adversity quotient response profiles by marital status reveals that married individuals tend to display a higher level of responsibility compared to other marital statuses. Married respondents have the largest numbers in the "Quickly Pass" and "Be Limited to this Situation" categories, with 102 and 100 individuals respectively, reflecting a tendency towards moderate responsibility. Single individuals show lower numbers across all categories, with only 1 in the "Completely Responsible" category and 20 in "Quickly Pass." Widows exhibit minimal responses, with only 7 total responses, while separated individuals have no recorded responses. Overall, married individuals show a more responsible approach to adversity, while singles and widows demonstrate less engagement in the higher responsibility categories.

D. Length of Service

Length of Service	Adversity Quotient Response Profile					Total
	Completely Responsible	Quickly Pass	Be Limited to this Situation	Responsible	Not Responsible at all	
5 yrs. and below	4	18	27	3	1	53
6-10	2	43	38	4	1	88
11-15	2	35	23	4	0	64
16-20	0	15	24	0	1	40
21-25	2	6	12	1	0	20
26 and above	0	9	6	0	0	15
Total	9	126	130	12	3	280

The data on adversity quotient response profiles by length of service indicates that employees with shorter service durations (5 years and below) tend to show a higher level of responsibility compared to those with longer service. The 5 years and below group has the highest number of individuals in the "Be Limited to this Situation" category (27), while also showing a moderate number in "Completely Responsible" (4). In contrast, employees with 6-10 years of service have a larger presence in the "Quickly Pass" category (43) but fewer in "Completely Responsible" (2). Those with 11-15 years of service demonstrate a balanced profile with notable numbers in "Quickly Pass" (35) and "Be Limited to this Situation" (23). Employees with longer service (16-20 years and above) show reduced numbers overall, with the longest service group (26 and above) having the least total responses. Generally, shorter service employees are more engaged in responsible categories, while longer service employees show a decline in higher responsibility responses.

E. Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Adversity Quotient Response Profile					
	Completely Responsible	Quickly Pass	Be Limited to this Situation	Responsible	Not Responsible at all	Total
College Level	0	2	2	0	0	4
College Graduate	9	118	129	12	3	271
Masters with Units	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master Degree Holder	0	3	0	0	0	3
LLB with units	0	2	0	0	0	2
PhD with units	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	9	125	131	12	3	280

The data on adversity quotient response profiles by educational attainment shows that college graduates exhibit the most varied and responsible profiles. College graduates have the highest numbers in the "Quickly Pass" (118) and "Be Limited to this Situation" (129) categories, reflecting a tendency to handle adversity with moderate responsibility. In contrast, individuals with lower educational attainment, such as college level (4 responses total), show very few instances of high responsibility and a predominance in the "Be Limited to this Situation" category. Those with master's degrees, LLB with units, and PhD with units have very few responses, suggesting minimal data and limited representation. Overall, higher educational attainment, particularly at the college graduate level, is associated with a more balanced and responsible approach to adversity.

F. No. of Children

No. of Children	Adversity Quotient Response Profile					
	Completely Responsible	Quickly Pass	Be Limited to this Situation	Responsible	Not Responsible at all	Total
None	1	21	28	3	1	54
1-3	9	90	78	8	2	286
4-6	0	14	20	2	0	36
7-10	0	1	3	0	0	4
Total	9	126	129	13	3	280

The data on adversity quotient response profiles by number of children reveals that individuals with 1-3 children exhibit the highest level of responsibility, with a notable number categorized as "Quickly Pass" (90) and "Be Limited to this Situation" (78). In contrast, individuals with no children show fewer high-responsibility responses, with the majority in the "Be Limited to this Situation" category (28). Those with 4-6 children have a smaller total number of responses and show a trend towards less responsibility, while individuals with 7-10 children have the least representation and also exhibit minimal responses across all categories. Overall, having 1-3 children is associated with a higher level of responsible handling of adversity, while having more or fewer children correlates with a less engaged or responsible approach.

G. No. of Dependents

No. of Dependents	Adversity Quotient Response Profile					
	Completely Responsible	Quickly Pass	Be Limited to this Situation	Responsible	Not Responsible at all	Total
None	0	13	22	4	0	39
1-3	8	86	81	5	2	182
4-6	1	24	22	3	1	51
7-10	0	3	5	0	0	8
Total	9	126	130	12	3	280

The data on adversity quotient response profiles by number of dependents shows that individuals with 1-3 dependents generally exhibit a higher level of responsibility. This group has the highest numbers in the "Quickly Pass" (86) and "Be Limited to this Situation" (81) categories. Those with no dependents show fewer high-responsibility responses, with the majority categorized as "Be Limited to this Situation" (22). Individuals with 4-6 dependents also demonstrate a responsible approach but with fewer responses overall. Those with 7-10 dependents have the least representation and show minimal engagement in the responsibility categories. Overall, having 1-3 dependents is associated with a more responsible approach to adversity, while having more or fewer dependents correlates with a less consistent or responsible handling of adversity.

Table VI. Summary of Correlation Between Police Officers Adversity Quotient Response Profile and Their Demographic Profile

Item	Computed Value	Tabular Value	Correlation	Test of Null Hypothesis
Age	14.14	26.296	Insignificant	Accepted
Gender	4.20	9.488	Insignificant	Accepted
Marital Status	3.65	21.026	Insignificant	Accepted
Length of Service	20.40	31.410	Insignificant	Accepted
Educational Attainment	6.71	31.410	Insignificant	Accepted
No. of Children	7.48	21.026	Insignificant	Accepted
No. of Dependent	11.48	21.026	Insignificant	Accepted

Table 6 presents the summary of correlation between police officers' adversity quotient response profiles and their demographic profiles. The computed values for the correlation between adversity quotient responses and demographic factors are as follows: age (14.14), gender (4.20), marital status (3.65), length of service (20.40), educational attainment (6.71), number of children (7.48), and number of dependents (11.48). All computed values are compared to their respective tabular values: age (26.296), gender (9.488), marital status (21.026), length of service (31.410), educational attainment

(31.410), number of children (21.026), and number of dependents (21.026). Since all computed values are lower than the tabular values, the correlations are considered insignificant. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant correlation between the adversity quotient response profiles and the demographic factors, is accepted for all the categories.

Table VII
Responses of Police Officers on Their Level of Burnout in Terms of Emotional Exhaustion Subscale

ITEMS	7		6		5		4		3		2		1		WM	Desc	Rank
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%			
Emotional Exhaustion (EE) Subscale																	
1	22	7.86	72	25.71	20	7.14	57	20.36	25	8.93	40	14.28	44	15.71	3.98	FTM	2
2	26	9.32	67	24.01	44	15.77	44	15.77	32	11.47	50	17.92	16	5.73	4.27	FTM	1
3	14	5.00	45	16.07	45	16.07	46	16.43	48	17.14	58	20.71	24	8.57	3.79	FTM	3
4	11	3.99	22	7.97	20	7.25	36	13.04	24	8.70	66	23.91	97	35.14	2.73	OML	4
5	15	5.42	37	13.36	35	12.64	47	16.97	39	14.04	65	23.46	39	14.04	3.54	OML	6
6	6	2.17	29	10.51	35	12.68	35	12.68	26	9.42	75	27.17	70	25.36	3.00	OML	9
7	13	4.66	45	16.13	40	14.34	40	14.34	48	17.20	64	22.94	29	10.39	3.66	FTM	5
8	7	2.53	25	9.02	49	17.69	30	10.83	36	13.00	85	30.68	45	16.24	3.20	OML	7
9	13	4.64	25	8.93	34	12.14	28	10.00	37	13.21	89	31.78	54	19.28	3.09	OML	8
Average Weighted Mean															3.47	OML	

Legend

#	Description	Code	Range
7	Everyday	E	6.17-7.0
6	A Few Times a Week	FTW	5.31-6.16
5	Once a Week	OW	4.45-5.30
4	A Few Times Month	FTM	3.59-4.44
3	Once a Month or Less	OML	2.73-3.58
2	A Few Times a Year	FTY	1.87-2.72
1	Never	N	1.0-1.86

Table 7 shows that police officers report a moderate level of burnout in terms of emotional exhaustion, with an average weighted mean of 3.47, categorized as "Occasionally Moderate Level" (OML). The highest level of emotional exhaustion is associated with Item 2, which has a weighted mean of 4.27, indicating it is "Frequently True for Me" (FTM). Item 1 follows with a mean of 3.98, also categorized as "FTM." Items 3 and 7 are similarly rated with weighted means of 3.79 and 3.66, respectively, indicating frequent emotional exhaustion. In contrast, Items 4 and 6 have the lowest means, 2.73 and 3.00, respectively, reflecting a less severe level of burnout. Overall, while there are some variations, the data suggests that emotional exhaustion is a notable concern among police officers, with significant variation across different aspects of their work.

Table VIII**Level of Burnout in Terms of Personal Accomplishment as Responded by Police Officers**

ITEMS	7		6		5		4		3		2		1		WM	Desc	Rank
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%			
Personal Accomplishment (PA) Subscale																	
1	126	45.00	80	28.57	30	10.71	25	8.93	12	4.28	3	1.07	4	1.43	5.92	FTW	2
2	90	32.61	88	31.88	35	12.68	35	12.68	19	6.88	3	1.09	6	2.17	5.59	FTW	6
3	111	39.64	90	32.14	39	13.93	22	7.86	7	2.50	8	2.86	3	1.07	5.54	FTW	7
4	132	47.14	89	31.78	27	9.64	16	5.71	7	2.50	7	2.50	2	.71	6.05	FTW	1
5	92	33.45	98	35.64	53	19.27	16	5.82	7	2.54	7	2.54	2	.73	5.81	FTW	3.5
6	61	22.18	85	30.91	50	18.18	34	12.36	23	8.36	12	4.36	1.0	3.64	5.18	OW	8
7	94	33.57	110	39.28	35	12.50	25	8.93	7	2.50	5	1.78	4	1.43	5.81	FTW	3.5
8	84	30.32	108	38.99	38	13.72	25	9.02	8	2.89	9	3.25	5	1.80	5.68	FTW	5
9	31	11.36	50	18.32	52	19.05	35	12.82	24	8.79	28	10.26	53	19.41	4.02	FTM	9.5
10	26	9.39	57	20.58	49	17.69	39	14.08	28	10.11	28	10.11	50	18.05	4.02	FTM	9.5
11	18	6.47	43	15.47	55	19.78	48	17.27	38	13.67	37	13.31	39	14.03	3.88	FTM	11
12	14	5.03	30	10.79	33	11.87	22	7.91	19	6.83	43	15.47	117	42.09	2.84	OML	13
13	13	4.68	24	8.63	30	10.79	34	12.23	26	9.35	56	20.14	95	34.17	2.90	OML	12
Average Weighted Mean															4.86	OW	

Table 8 indicates that police officers generally experience a moderate level of personal accomplishment, with an average weighted mean of 4.86, categorized as "Occasionally Weak" (OW). Among the items, Item 4 has the highest weighted mean of 6.05, suggesting that officers frequently feel a strong sense of personal accomplishment in this area. Items 1 and 5 also rank high with means of 5.92 and 5.81, respectively, reflecting frequent feelings of accomplishment. Conversely, Items 12 and 13 have the lowest means of 2.84 and 2.90, indicating that these aspects of personal accomplishment are experienced less frequently, with "Occasionally Moderate Level" (OML) descriptions. Overall, while some areas show strong feelings of personal accomplishment, there are notable variations, with certain aspects being less satisfying for officers.

TABLE IX**Perceptions of Police Officers with Regard to the Level of Burnout in Terms of Depersonalization Subscale**

ITEMS	7		6		5		4		3		2		1		WM	Desc	Rank
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%			
Depersonalization (DP) Subscale																	
1	23	8.30	34	12.27	25	9.02	26	9.39	22	7.94	34	12.27	113	40.79	3.03	OML	3
2	22	7.88	30	10.75	28	10.04	29	10.39	30	10.75	68	24.37	72	25.81	3.16	OML	2
3	14	5.05	27	9.75	24	8.66	40	14.44	65	23.46	46	16.61	61	22.02	3.20	OML	1
4	8	2.89	18	6.50	12	4.33	15	5.42	23	8.30	46	16.61	155	55.96	2.17	FTY	5
5	10	3.62	19	6.88	14	5.07	18	6.52	23	8.33	72	26.09	120	43.48	2.39	FTY	4
Average Weighted Mean															2.78	OML	

Table 9 reveals police officers' perceptions of burnout in terms of the Depersonalization (DP) subscale, with an overall average weighted mean of 2.78, categorized as "Occasionally Moderate Level" (OML). Among the items, Item 3 has the highest mean of 3.20, indicating that it is perceived as the most frequent source of depersonalization. Item 2 follows with a mean of 3.16, reflecting moderate frequency in depersonalization experiences. In contrast, Items 4 and 5, with means of 2.17 and 2.39 respectively, are perceived as less frequent sources of depersonalization, categorized as "Frequently True for You" (FTY). Overall, while there is a moderate perception of depersonalization, it is less severe compared to other burnout dimensions.

Table X
Correlation on Police Officers Responses on the Level of Burnout and Demographic Profile

A. Age

Age	Level of Burnout							Total
	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	
25 years old and below	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	3
26-30 years old	2	1	11	25	20	23	0	71
31-40 years old	4	11	18	42	47	9	0	131
41-50 years old	1	1	5	25	19	6	0	57
51 years old and above	0	2	3	1	8	4	0	18
Total	7	15	37	94	96	31	0	280

The data shows that the level of burnout among police officers varies significantly with age. Officers aged 31-40 years old exhibit the highest burnout levels, with substantial representation across all burnout levels, particularly in categories 4 and 5. In contrast, those aged 26-30 years old report moderate levels of burnout, while officers aged 41-50 and 51 years old and above report lower overall burnout levels. The youngest group (25 years old and below) shows minimal burnout.

B. Gender

Gender	Level of Burnout							Total
	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	
Male	5	9	17	55	65	24	0	175
Female	2	6	18	39	31	9	0	105
Total	7	15	35	94	96	33	0	280

The data shows that male officers experience higher levels of burnout compared to female officers, with significant numbers in levels 4 and 5. Female officers generally report lower burnout levels, with the highest frequency in level 4. Both genders show a similar distribution of burnout levels, but males tend to have higher burnout scores overall.

C. Marital Status

Marital Status	Level of Burnout							
	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	Total
Single	1	3	3	16	18	8	0	49
Married	6	13	30	76	72	28	0	225
Widow	0	0	1	2	2	1	0	6
Separated	0	0	0	00	0	0	0	0
Total	7	16	34	94	92	37	0	180

The data shows that married police officers exhibit the highest levels of burnout, particularly in levels 4 and 5. Single officers also experience burnout, but to a lesser extent. Widowed officers report minimal burnout, and there are no data for separated officers, indicating a lack of response or relevance in this category.

D. Length of Service

Length of Service	Level of Burnout							
	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	Total
5 yrs and below	3	1	10	18	16	5	0	53
6-10	2	8	9	23	31	15	0	88
11-15	1	4	7	25	22	5	0	64
16-20	1	1	7	12	15	4	0	40
21-25	0	0	3	7	8	2	0	20
26 and above	0	2	0	4	7	2	0	15
Total	7	16	36	89	99	33	0	280

The data shows that police officers with 6-10 years of service report the highest levels of burnout, particularly in levels 4 and 5. Officers with 5 years and below shows considerable burnout as well, but the levels decrease for those with longer service durations, suggesting that burnout might be more acute in the mid-range of service length.

E. Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Level of Burnout							Total
	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	
College Level	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	4
College Graduate	7	16	32	94	91	31	0	271
Masters with Units	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master Degree Holder	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	3
LLB with units	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
PhD with units	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	7	17	34	95	94	33	0	280

The data shows that college graduates exhibit the highest levels of burnout, particularly in levels 4 and 5. Officers with only college-level education or higher degrees report lower burnout levels, with the lowest levels observed among those with Master's or advanced degrees. The data indicates that higher educational attainment does not necessarily correlate with increased burnout.

F. No. of Children

No. of Children	Level of Burnout							Total
	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	
None	1	2	5	18	20	8	0	54
1-3	6	8	25	63	61	23	0	186
4-6	0	6	3	10	13	4	0	36
7-10	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	4
Total	7	16	34	93	95	35	0	280

The data shows that officers with 1-3 children report the highest levels of burnout, especially in levels 4 and 5. Those with no children and 4-6 children experience lower levels of burnout, while those with 7-10 children report the least burnout. This suggests that having more children may be associated with lower burnout levels, possibly due to fewer pressures in the workplace.

G. No. of Dependents

No. of Dependents	Level of Burnout							Total
	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	
None	1	4	2	17	11	4	0	39
1-3	6	7	26	63	64	16	0	182
4-6	0	5	4	10	22	10	0	51
7-10	0	0	2	3	2	1	0	8
Total	7	16	34	93	99	31	0	280

The data shows that officers with 1-3 dependents experience the highest burnout levels, particularly in levels 4 and 5. Those with no dependents report lower burnout levels, while those with 4-6 dependents show moderate levels of burnout. The trend indicates that a higher number of dependents correlates with increased burnout.

Table XI. Summary of Correlation Between Level of Burnout and Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Items	Computed Value	Tabular Value	Correlation	Test of Hypothesis
Age	24.65	36.415	Insignificant	Accepted
Gender	6.10	12.592	Insignificant	Accepted
Marital Status	3.18	28.869	Insignificant	Accepted
Length of Service	21.32	43.773	Insignificant	Accepted
Educational Attainment	11.81	43.773	Insignificant	Accepted
No. of Children	33.74	28.869	Significant	Rejected
No. of Dependents	19.84	28.869	Insignificant	Accepted

As reflected in Table 11, it revealed that the correlation regarding level of burnout and demographic profile of the respondents, only the number of children was significantly correlated, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis. This signified that police officer who have children are more prone to burnout than those who have none. On the other hand, the demographic profile of the respondents namely age, gender, marital status, length of service, educational attainment, and number of dependents were insignificantly correlated due to their tabular values being greater than their computed values. This means that they do not affect the level of burnout of police officers.

Table XII. Correlation Between Adversity Quotient Response Profile and Level of Burnout

Level of Burnout	Adversity Quotient Response Profile					
	Completely Responsible	Quickly Pass	Be Limited to the Situation	Responsible	Not Responsible at All	Total
Every day	0	6	4	0	0	10
A Few Times a Week	0	5	9	0	0	14
Once a Week	2	26	25	3	2	58
A Few Times a Month	4	49	49	4	1	107
Once a Month or Less	1	32	34	5	0	72
A Few Times a Year	2	6	10	0	0	18
Never	0	0	1	0	0	1
Total	9	124	132	12	3	280

Table 12 reveals a correlation between the Adversity Quotient Response Profile and the level of burnout among police officers. The majority of officers who experience burnout "A Few Times a Month" and "Once a Month or Less" tend to limit their response to the situation, with 49 and 34 officers respectively reporting this response. Those who experience burnout "Once a Week" also predominantly limit their response to the situation. Very few officers feel completely responsible or not responsible at all across all levels of burnout. The data suggests that most officers tend to respond to burnout by limiting their responsibility to the situation, with a smaller proportion responding more actively or passively.

DISCUSSION

Findings

The results of the study are as follows:

Profile of Respondents

Around forty-six (46) percent of the respondent police officers are in the age 30 to 40, twenty-five (25) percent are 26 to 30 years old, and twenty (20) percent are 41 to 50 years old. On the other hand, the population of police officers comprises 62.5 percent male and only 37.5 percent female officers. Further, around eighty (80) percent of the

respondent police officers are married. The length of service of the majority of the police officers is 6 to 15 years. Around 96 percent of the respondent police officers are college graduates. Lastly, majority of the respondents have 1 to 3 children and/or dependents.

Adversity Response Profile of Police Officers

Adversity Response Profile of Police Officers has a mean score of 137.2 which falls on the average level. Control has a score of 3.41 which means that police officers found themselves often in control of the adverse situations they encounter. Meanwhile, Ownership has a score of 3.69 which means that the police officers found themselves often responsible for the adverse situation they encounter. Reach has a score of 3.21 which means that police officers found that adverse situations sometimes affect some aspects of their lives. Lastly, Endurance has a score of 3.48 which means that police officers found the effects of adverse situation often pass.

Level of Burnout of Police Officers

The police officers have obtained an average weighted mean of 3.47 level of burnout in terms of emotional exhaustion subscale. This portrayed that the police officers of Bohol experience emotional exhaustion once a month or less. On the other hand, the level of burnout in terms of personal accomplishment of police officers is 4.86. This means that police officers feel indifference or have distant attitude toward work once a week. Lastly, the level of burnout of police officers in terms of depersonalization subscale was 2.78. This means that police officers take a hardened, unfeeling approach toward the client at work once a month or less.

There is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of police officers and their adversity response profile. Additionally, it was revealed that the correlation regarding the level of burnout and demographic profile of the respondents, only the number of children was significantly correlated. Finally, it was found that the Level of Burnout has no significant relationship with the Adversity Response Profile of Police Officers in Bohol.

Conclusions

The demographic profile of police officers has no impact on their Adversity Response Profile. Moreover, only the number of children affects the level of burnout of police officers. Lastly, the Level of Burnout has no impact on the Adversity Response Profile of Police Officers in Bohol.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, the researcher advances the following recommendations:

The Philippine National Police should create a platform that encourages police officers to report any emotional or mental impact of the stressors they are constantly exposed to. Also, there should be seminars on mental health to police officers of Bohol so they will be taught any preventive or proactive strategies to deal with the stress directly related to police work.

The Chief of Police in every station in Bohol should coordinate with institutions that provide mental health awareness for a more responsive and effective coping strategies. Additionally, there should be promotion of culture that allows police officers to express their feelings of isolation, depression, and anxiety, thus preventing them to use maladaptive mechanisms that can be harmful to their mental health in the long run.

Furthermore, to verify the findings of this study, future researchers may delve into the social support on the adversity response of police officers in relation to their level of burnout in terms of emotional exhaustion, cynicism, and depersonalization in all police stations of the Bohol province.

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